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Insulating Characteristics and Ionic Conductivity Properties of the Solid Electrolyte Interface in Lithium-Ion Batteries to Improve a Redox-Mediated Enhanced Coulometry Method

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The Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) in lithium-ion batteries plays a critical role in key performance indicators such as cycle life and the significance of its ionic conductivity and electrically-protecting character. The SEI layer's chemical composition and structure significantly influence its ionic conductivity, and various strategies exist to enhance its electrically-protecting character while maintaining adequate ionic conductivity. Herein, a Redox-Mediated Enhanced Coulometry method is presented, which enables evaluation of both protecting character and ionic conductivity of the SEI, which allows estimation of cycle life at various temperatures. The method is based on the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) technique and coulombic efficiency measurements in the presence of redox mediators. The impact of electrolyte additives at different temperatures has been used to demonstrate the potential of the proposed method.

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The reliability and safety of lithium-ion batteries (LiB) depend heavily on the Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) stability and functionality, acting as a barrier that separates the lithium-ion negative electrode from the electrolyte and maintains the electrode's surface stability.¹ The ionic conductivity of the SEI layer is a crucial aspect that significantly impacts battery performance, capacity, and safety.²

The ionic conductivity of the SEI layer relies on several factors, including the thickness and morphology of the layer, the layer's component nature and the electrolyte type.^{3,4} Higher ionic conductivity in the SEI layer enhances lithium ions' diffusion through it, leading to a more efficient charge and discharge process and better battery performance. In contrast, low ionic conductivity generates internal resistance, limiting the battery's power output and capacity. Although high ionic conductivity in the SEI layer improves the battery's performance and capacity, it can compromise its electrically protecting character, which is critical in preventing accelerated capacity decay and electrochemical processes that could result in battery failure. Therefore, researchers and battery manufacturers are trying to balance the SEI's ionic conductivity and its electrically-protecting character carefully. Recent studies indicate that the SEI's chemical composition and structure significantly influence its ionic conductivity. Additives such as fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC) can enhance the SEI's ionic conductivity, reducing resistive phase formation and facilitating lithium ion diffusion.^{5,6}

There are several strategies to enhance the SEI's electrically protecting character while maintaining adequate ionic conductivity. For example, controlling the C-rate, temperature or voltage during the SEI formation, as well as with the use of electrolyte additives that can form an efficient protective layer on the anode surface, maintaining high ionic conductivity in the SEI.^{7–10}

Although the determination of intrinsic properties of the SEI layer is challenging due to its thinness and inaccessibility, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)^{11,12} provides information on the ionic conductivity of the SEI layer. Other techniques such as atomic force microscopy (AFM),^{13,14} scanning electron microscopy (SEM)¹⁵ or X-

ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)¹⁶ can provide information on the SEI's morphology and composition, aiding to correlate the properties of the SEI with its composition or morphology.

Regarding the electrically-protecting character of the SEI, we have developed a methodology in a previous paper to determine the protection performance of the nanolayer SEI.¹⁷ In this paper, we proposed a new technique, called Redox-Mediated Enhanced Coulometry, for probing the protecting character of the SEI by adding a redox mediator that leads to an internal self-discharge process that results in an easily measurable decrease in coulombic efficiency. While this method was demonstrated to be a powerful accelerated electrochemical technique for searching advanced additives, the ionic resistance of the resulting SEI was overseen. However, for battery electrolytes to achieve high performance, they must lead to the formation of an SEI with exceptional protective properties, such as high electrical resistance and excellent ionic conductivity.

In this work, we expand on this concept by assessing the protecting character of the Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) and determining the film's ionic conductivity to better estimate the electrochemical performance of the resulting battery. To achieve this, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is conducted in the absence of a redox mediator to determine the ionic resistivity of the SEI, which is followed by coulombic efficiency measurement in the presence of the redox mediator to assess the protecting character. In this way, both protecting character and ionic resistivity are obtained. The modified method is effectively employed in the exploration of electrolyte additives across different temperature ranges, thereby demonstrating the feasibility and potential of this novel approach.

Experimental

Preparation of pouch cells.—Commercial 200 mAh lithium-ion pouch cells containing LiFePO₄ (Lithium Iron Phosphate—LFP) positive electrodes and artificial graphite negative electrodes separated by a Celgard material were acquired in dry form from LiFUN Technology (Xinma Industry Zone, Golden Dragon Road, Tianyuan District, Zhuzhou City, Hunan Province, PRC, 412 000). Two types of pouch cells fabrication procedures, batch 1 and batch 2, were used. The pouch cell construction is the same until the degasification step, in which the redox mediator was added in batch 1 to analyze

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Figure 1. Schematic procedure of two cell batches.

Figure 2. dQ/dV versus voltage during formation stage.

SEI electrical isolating character and no additions in the batch 2, which will be used for SEI ionic conductivity evaluation. Figure 1 shows the configuration of the 2 test batches.

The preparation for both batches started by filling the cells under an argon atmosphere with 1 ml of different electrolyte formulations using a syringe. The control electrolyte (CTRL) was 1M LiPF₆ in EC:DEC (1:1), anhydrous, from Solvionic. For electrolytes with additive, 2% or 6% in weight of vinylene carbonate, anhydrous, and fluoroethylene carbonate, anhydrous, from Sigma Aldrich were added to CTRL electrolyte to formulate three different electrolytes, 2VC, 6VC and 2FEC, respectively. To facilitate discussion, pouch cells assembled with additives in the electrolyte are denoted as the additive concentration in %. The final step of the cell assembling procedure was a 6 s sealing at 170 °C under a vacuum at -90 kPa by a vacuum sealer (TOB-YF2000 Vacuum Sealing Machine).

A wetting step was carried out by applying 1.5 V for 24 h with a Neware battery tester BTS4000-5V6A-8CH model (Shenzhen Neware Corporation, China). Then, cells were transferred into a climatic chamber (Angelantoni Discovery ACS DY250) at 40 °C and an SEI formation protocol was performed. The formation procedure consisted of applying a C/20 constant current until 3.65 V followed by a constant voltage for 1 h. The discharge step was carried out by applying a C/20 constant current until 65% state of charge (SoC) was reached.

Cells were then transferred into the glove box and were opened to remove the gas generated in the SEI formation. During this step, 0.5 ml of the electrolyte-containing redox mediator (300 mM of *m*-methyl phthalimide, PHT, Sigma Aldrich) was added to the first batch to evaluate SEI electrical isolating character. In contrast, mediator was not added only to the second batch and cells were only opened to remove the gas. Then, all the batteries were closed by a vacuum sealer to improve the electrolyte distribution as was mentioned above.

Electrochemical experiments.—In order to evaluate the electrical isolation properties of the SEI, coulombic efficiency (CE) was measured. This was done by cycling the first batch of samples for five cycles at a rate of C/3, between 2.50 and 3.55 V, at three different temperatures 20, 40, and 55 °C. More details of this method could be found in Ref. 17.

On the other hand, to evaluate SEI ionic conductivity, EIS was carried out to the second batch at 50 % SoC and different temperatures, 20, 40, and 55 °C. EIS was performed by a potentiostat (BioLogic, Model-VSP) using a potentiostatic mode with 10 mV of amplitude and a frequency range from 1.5 kHz to 20 mHz. Then, for the aging experiment, batteries from this batch 2 were cycled at 20 °C following a regime of 1C or at 55 °C and C/3 from 2.50 and 3.65 V. Then, EIS was carried out at 20 °C for the batch cycled at 55 °C.

Differential capacity curves of the different electrolyte samples were performed aiming to elucidate additives' roles in the SEI formation process and infer information about the mechanism of the electrolyte decomposition on the electrode's surface.

Results

Differential capacity (dQ/dV).—Generally, the full cell voltage versus capacity data contains thermodynamic information from both electrodes as an average. Here to separate the electrode information and electrolyte reductions, we have used dQ/dV which represent peaks from the phase transitions in the electrodes and from the electrolyte and additive reduction. In Fig. 2, a plot of the dQ/dV versus voltage for electrolytes containing 2 wt% and 6 wt% of VC, 2 wt% of FEC and the control, during the formation stage is given from the 2 to 3 V region.

The CTRL sample contains two reduction peaks at 2.60 and 2.72 V that can be assigned to electrolyte reduction, generating organic and inorganic products.^{18,19} The addition of 2 wt% of VC revealed a distinct 2.10 V shoulder, indicating the reduction of VC. Interestingly, the absence of the first peak and the presence of a second peak at lower potential indicate that VC impedes partially the

process. This behavior has been described previously and suggests the formation of an SEI involving VC by-products such as poly(VC) and Li_2CO_3 ^{20–22} along with electrolyte reduction products. When the VC concentration is increased, the peaks were drastically reduced. This may be because electrolyte VC-saturated reduces the side reactions. Regarding the FEC-content electrolytes, it seems that it reduced the electrolyte decomposition much more than VC-content electrolytes leading to an SEI, that according to the literature, is based on poly(FEC), Li_2CO_3 , LiF and H_2 .²³

SEI electrically-insulating characteristics.—In order to further analyze the additive's role in the Li-ion cell's cyclability, we evaluate the protecting character of the SEI formed on the negative electrode of the batteries by introducing a redox molecule, which increases the self-discharge rate. Indeed, the presence of the redox molecule resulted in a reduction of the coulombic efficiency (CE) of the LFP-Graphite battery for CTRL electrolyte (Fig. 3).

Specifically, we observed a decrease from approximately 99.9% to ca. 80% at the three tested temperatures (20, 40 and 55 °C), indicating that, as expected, in the absence of additives, charge transfer across the SEI in the presence of the redox molecule was not efficiently prevented.

The addition of electrolyte additives such as VC and FEC significantly enhances the protecting character of the solid electrolyte interphase significantly increased regardless of the temperature. It seems that, under all temperature conditions, the addition of VC allows reaching the optimal conditions to form a more effective SEI since coulombic efficiency values above 99% were obtained for both VC-content electrolyte (2VC and 6VC). Nevertheless, electrolytes

prepared with 2 wt% of FEC also resulted beneficial as the coulombic efficiencies increased from 80% to 97%. Interestingly, at the highest temperature (55 °C - Fig. 3c), the most protecting character was obtained for the electrolyte formation containing 6 wt% of VC.

SEI ionic conductivity properties.—The SEI protecting character is not the only main property of a good SEI. Moreover, it must ease the Li (de-) intercalation process to avoid Li reduction phenomena. Thus, EIS was employed to perform an in-depth analysis of the charge transfer resistance for Li (de-) intercalation. Results are shown in Fig. 4 where the Nyquist plots for 200 mAh batteries with and without additives are represented. Spectra from the batteries show different shapes depending on temperature conditions: at 20 °C, one semicircle at high frequencies and one at mid frequencies are observed. While, generally, at 40 and 55 °C only one semicircle at high-mid frequencies is detected. In some samples, the semicircle at lower frequencies is followed by a 45° line at low frequencies. The results were fitted according to the equivalent circuit model shown in Fig. S1, where one ohmic resistance (R_{ohm}) that is defined where the plot crosses the horizontal axis at high frequencies, and generally attributed to the electrolyte solution, is coupled in series with two RC circuits, the first is assigned to the passivated film (R_{SEI}), while the second is considered to be a charge-transfer resistance ($R_{CT,SEI}$) and, finally, a Warburg element in series which represents the diffusion in the electrode.^{24,25} As the temperature increased, the resistance from the first semicircle decreased until disappeared. Thus, the results were fitted with one RC circuit related to the charge transfer resistance. The calculated resistances for the

Figure 3. Electrically insulating characteristics by coulombic efficiency at 20 °C (a), 40 °C (b) and 55 °C (c).

Figure 4. Nyquist plot of EIS measurements of fresh cells at 20 °C (a), 40 °C (b) and 55 °C (c). Experimental data are represented by diamonds and fitted data are represented by lines.

different batteries tested are listed in Tables S2, S3 and S4 in the Supplementary Information. Nyquist plots indicate that the first semicircle remains unchanged in spite of changes in the electrolyte composition while the second semicircle showed sensitivity to the additive presence. This was expected because the influence of vinylene carbonate (VC) and fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC) in SEI-forming of the battery cells is already well known.^{26,27}

Additives have not shown a significant impact in the R_{SEI} values. In contrast, $R_{CT,SEI}$ provided more information since the major additives effect was the electrode surface modification due to SEI compounds, which lead into a changes in the ion transport. Thus, $R_{CT,SEI}$ can be used as an SEI ionic conductivity measurement.

The highest $R_{CT,SEI}$ values were obtained with VC-content electrolytes. However, 6VC electrolytes showed a resistance four times higher compared to 2VC electrolytes. On the other hand, 2FEC electrolytes provided a similar resistance to CTRL electrolytes. The temperature showed a clear effect in the $R_{CT,SEI}$ as expected since all

electrolytes reduced their resistance significantly. Moreover, the difference between the highest (6VC) and the lowest (CTRL) $R_{CT,SEI}$ values was also reduced from 10 to 2 times, therefore, the effect of $R_{CT,SEI}$ should be reduced with high temperature.

Cycling aging.—Batteries tested with electrolyte formulation without additive (CTRL), and with 2VC, 2FEC at 20 °C did not exhibit significant capacity fading during the 200-cycles tested (Fig. 5a). Nevertheless, 6VC electrolytes showed critical capacity fading of 20%, consequently, the effect of adding an excess of VC was detrimental. When comparing these results to those obtained at 55 °C, a distinct trend emerges, with all the formulations containing additive delivering acceptable capacity retention of 95% after 100 cycles (Fig. 5b) while CTRL electrolytes lost a 25% of capacity.

When examining the behavior of charge transfer resistance in the cells at high temperatures, it can be observed that as aging proceeds the $R_{CT,SEI}$ increases substantially in the CTRL electrolyte,

Figure 5. Life cycle performance at 20 °C (a) and 55 °C (b).

surpassing 200 mOhm (see the resistance values of aged cells compiled in Table S4. in the Supporting Information). This pattern was anticipated due to the low capacity retention observed for this type of additive-free electrolyte after 100 cycles. In contrast, 2VC and 2FEC electrolytes showed no significant changes in the $R_{CT,SEI}$ while maintaining high capacity retention. However, having similar capacity retention, the charge transfer resistance of the 6VC electrolyte experienced considerable growth to more than 500 mOhm. Figure 6 summarises the Nyquist results of the 100 cycles-aged cells at 55 °C.

Discussion

SEI properties.—Regardless of the operating temperature, the SEI formed using the CTRL electrolyte composition resulted in the lowest resistance, consequently, the reduction products generated during the initial formation process in the CTRL electrolyte facilitate the Li (de-) intercalation albeit without providing any electrolyte protection. However, FEC electrolytes show a similar $R_{CT,SEI}$ with a higher protecting character. This fact reveals the importance of the type of structure forming the interphase layer, during the initial formation process that most Li-ion cells are put through after assembly. According to these results, FEC electrolytes reduced substantially the side reactions in the electrolyte, meaning that FEC by-products on the negative electrode are responsible for the high conductivity and high protecting character of the SEI.

Regarding the vinylene carbonate functionality, 2VC led to forming a layer that still has a low resistance, slightly higher than 2FEC, but with a much higher protecting character than CTRL electrolytes and higher than 2FEC. Saturating in VC (6 wt%) appears unfavorable as it leads to a drastic increase in the $R_{CT,SEI}$ without an increase in the protecting character regarding 2VC electrolytes. Moreover, 2VC did not prevent the electrolyte reduction as much as 6VC, therefore, the VC addition appeared to be responsible for the high resistance and highest protecting character. However, in normal conditions, the use of 6 wt% of VC may not be beneficial for the electrochemical performance of the battery cell due to the 5-fold increase in $R_{CT,SEI}$ with respect to the control electrolyte since could inhibit the Li (de-) intercalation. On the other hand, this could be avoided under operating conditions that require high temperatures, as all formulations, including 6VC electrolytes, demonstrated negligible resistances at 55 °C.

Figure 6. Nyquist plot of EIS measurements of aged cells at 20 °C of aged cells after having completed 100 cycles under 55 °C conditions.

According to the results obtained from the coulombic efficiency measurements and the ionic conductivity analysis, it can be concluded that the side reactions generated in the presence of FEC during the initial formation process provide more balance passivation and conductivity properties at 20 °C while VC by-products do it at high temperatures.

SEI properties determination by analyzing the electrically insulating characteristics and ionic conductivity.—The high $R_{CT,SEI}$ observed in 6VC electrolytes is reducing the (de-) intercalation kinetics, which is coherent with the high capacity fading after 200 cycles at 20 °C. Moreover, the vinylene carbonate saturation problems extend beyond its high initial resistance since the rapid increase in resistance contributes to accelerated capacity degradation at lower temperatures. This observation is further supported by the nature of compounds formed by vinylene carbonate during the

passivated film formation process, which are known to hinder the ion transport.²⁸

The lithium diffusion problem at 6 wt% of VC is solved at high temperatures, which is related to the low charge-transfer impedance ($R_{CT,SEI}$) measured at 55 °C and to the high protecting character observed in the SEI in these conditions. Thus, a clear trend between protecting character and cycle life can be observed since the VC-content electrolytes showed the highest efficiencies and the highest capacity retention at 55 °C follow by 2FEC electrolytes with close values of efficiency and capacity retention. This capacity retention trend is coherent with the results reported in the literature since is well-known the positive effect of VC for high temperatures experiments.²⁹ Then, the poorest protecting character from CTRL electrolytes is related to the poorest capacity retention.

This fact reveals the importance of simultaneously analyzing the electrically insulating characteristics and ionic conductivity properties of the solid electrolyte interface. According to these findings, it seems clear that as the operational temperature increase, the protecting character of the solid electrolyte interface layer gains importance, while the $R_{CT,SEI}$ loses relevance (e.g. 6 wt% VC). However, as temperature decrease, $R_{CT,SEI}$ gains importance since FEC-content electrolytes, with a good balance of protecting character and $R_{CT,SEI}$, have provided good results for middle and low temperatures^{29,30}

Therefore, the novel approach of combining redox-mediated coulometry and EIS measurements varying temperatures offers a more comprehensive understanding of the SEI properties. Simply assessing the protective nature or the $R_{CT,SEI}$ of the SEI is insufficient to accurately predict the cycle performance. By incorporating both techniques, a more holistic perspective is gained, enabling a more precise estimation of cycle performance in lithium-ion batteries.

Conclusions

This work has shown that the new methodology combining redox-mediated coulometry and EIS measurements provides fast and feasible information to formulate electrolytes for different working temperatures. The SEI protecting character and ionic conductivity are factors correlated with life cycle performance, however, the correlation is temperature dependent. The importance of ionic conductivity in correlation to cycle performance is reduced when batteries are under higher temperature conditions, while the protecting character of the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) layer gains importance in the performance. On the other hand, as the temperature decreases, ionic conductivity plays a more significant role in an initial characterization. Moreover, the evolution of ionic conductivity is another key factor at low temperatures, since it has been proved that VC could reduce the ionic conductivity drastically during cycling experiments without fading capacity.

Through our testing, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of this method in providing crucial information on the SEI layer's ionic conductivity and protecting character, which can be used to estimate the cycle life of lithium-ion. In addition, this technique could be useful to complement SEI composition analysis to understand with more accuracy which components provide electrically insulating character and/or conductivity at different temperatures.

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